

ACUTE TOXICOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT OF DIFETHIALONE IN INDIAN DESERT GERBIL, *MERIONES HURRIANAE*

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ABSTRACT

The acute median lethal dose, LD₅₀, is used as an indicator of a rodenticide's toxicity. The LD₅₀ when administered in acute toxicity tests is utilized for the classification of toxic potential of various rodenticides. The acute median lethal dose of the second generation anticoagulant, Difethialone to Indian Desert gerbil, *Meriones hurrianae* has been reported in this paper. The experiment was done by oral intubation method using five different dosages – 0.2 - 0.6 mg/kg body weight. The treated animals were held for 48 hours at room temperature with food and water *ad libitum*, after which the dead gerbils were counted. The LD₅₀ value was calculated to be 0.28mg/kg body weight by probit method.

Key Words: Difethialone, Indian Desert Gerbil, LD₅₀, *Meriones hurrianae*, Toxicity.

INTRODUCTION

Meriones hurrianae is a primarily seedivorous animal and is common in rain fed crop areas. It causes damage to the kharif crops during the sowing stage. They aggregate on the bunds and invade the crops causing immense damage. A toxic chemical of adequate potency should be applied at right time interval for the control of these gerbils. The requisites for effective rodent control are that a maximum kill should be achieved with a minimum quantity of the rodenticide. The United States Environment Protection Agency (EPA) requires the determination of LD₅₀ values of the toxic chemicals before they could be considered for registration as pesticides. The acute median lethal dose for the second generation anticoagulant rodenticides is much less than the first generation anticoagulant rodenticides indicating higher toxicity of second generation

anticoagulants. While comparing the acute LD₅₀ values in laboratory rats, Marsh et al. (1980) observed that the toxicity of Bromadiolone with LD₅₀ 1.12 mg/kg was 165 times more than Warfarin with LD₅₀ 180 mg/kg. Extensive use of Warfarin resulted in resistance among rodents. Warfarin resistance has also been reported in the Lesser Rice-field rat, *Rattus losea* (Wang et al., 2008). Also, to control the problem of resistance to first generation anticoagulants, a new class of second generation anticoagulants called 'superwarfarins' has been developed (Petterino and Paolo, 2001; Gebauer, 2007). These are brodifacoum, bromadiolone and difethialone. The oral LD₅₀ of Difethialone in three species of commensal rodents indicates there is not a notable difference between the sexes (Lechevin and Poche, 1988). The success of rodent control with rodenticides depends on the toxicity of the active ingredient used. The aim of this study is to elucidate the acute median lethal dose of

Difethialone against Indian desert gerbils, *Meriones hurrianae*.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Animals

A total of 25 acclimatized healthy adult gerbils, *Meriones hurrianae*, of combined sexes having approximately uniform weight were selected for the determination of acute oral median lethal dose (LD₅₀).

Experimental Setup

The experiment was carried out with a minimum range of 5 concentrations (0.2-0.6 mg/kg. body weight of the animals). The dose range was selected on the basis of No-choice feeding test. Stock solution of Difethialone was prepared in propylene glycol from the liquid concentrate of Difethialone (1.25 g/litre) supplied by LIPHA of France. Prior to the experiment, the gerbils were acclimatized to the laboratory conditions. During this period, they were fed with commercial pelleted diet (Rat Feed: Hindustan Lever Limited) and had access to fresh water *ad libitum*.

Dose preparation and administration

The animals were weighed and fasted 18 hours prior to the administration of the dose. A calculated quantity of the stock solution containing active ingredient according to the dose (0.2 - 0.6 mg/kg body weight) was administered once orally to each group of five gerbils by stomach tube feeding method. One group was also exposed to the vehicle control. The observations including the symptoms of Difethialone toxicity and days of death of each animal were recorded for 15 days.

The acute median lethal dose LD₅₀ was calculated using Finney's probit method, (1971).

RESULTS

The acute median lethal dose LD₅₀ was evaluated and computed for combined sexes of the test animals, Indian desert gerbils, *Meriones hurrianae* as there was non-significant difference in their mortality response. Initially, the animals do not show any significant symptoms of poisoning for the lowest dose i.e. 0.2 mg/kg body weight while at higher doses, signs of bleeding from eyes, nose and paws were observed with labored breathing and finally resulting into death. 100 percent mortality of all the animals was observed at 0.5 and 0.6 mg/kg body weight. The percentage of animals that died at each dose was then transformed to probit using Finney's method. The dose corresponding to probit 5, i.e., 50%, was found. The LD₅₀ value of Difethialone which when administered orally was evaluated as - 0.28 (0.24- 0.32 fiducial limits) mg/kg body weight. The results have been tabulated in the Table 1.

DISCUSSION

Lethal dosages of anticoagulants are determined to assess the efficacy of these compounds to various rodent species. The lower the LD₅₀ dose, the more toxic is the rodenticide. The LD₅₀ of Difethialone was found to be 0.28 mg/kg body weight of the test animal, *Meriones hurrianae*, indicating high toxicity of the candidate poison and its unprecedented potency and capability to control the gerbil population. This implies high susceptibility of gerbils to Difethialone. The results reveal that only a small requisite quantity of the rodenticide is effective for the rapid kill of the gerbils in few days. The usually slow onset of toxic effects of second generation anticoagulants allows the baits to be prepared with very low concentrations of active ingredient (Saxena, 2014). The above results find support with the observations of Sahni (1993), who recorded a low LD₅₀ of Difethialone (1.2 mg/kg. body weight) in albino mice (toxicity does not always scale with body mass and also there is

Table1. Rodenticidal Efficacy of Difethialone against *Meriones hurrianae* Jerdon

Test Compound	Regression Equation	Variance	χ^2 (df)	LD50 mg/kg b.wt. (Fiducial limits)
Difethialone	1.664+ 7.508X	0.000963	0.27 ₍₄₎	0.28(0.24-0.32)

df: degrees of freedom

variability in the response of different rodents). Difethialone's relatively rapid mode of action, coupled with excellent acceptance in the laboratory were confirmed in field trials in which infestation of Norway rats and Roof rats were treated with baits (Lechevin and Poche, 1988). In albino mice treated with Zinc phosphide before the oral administration of Difethialone, the LD₅₀ was observed to be much lower than in those which are being tested only for Difethialone toxicity (Mathur, 1994). The oral toxicity of Difethialone has not been worked out much for many rodent species. Difethialone has been reported a promising rodenticide against warfarin resistant and susceptible strains of *Rattus norvegicus* and *Mus musculus* (Nahas et al., 1989). In a secondary toxicity study of Difethialone to Barn owls, the toxic dose of Difethialone was found to be far less than the lethal doses reported for other anticoagulants viz. Brodifacoum, Difenacoum and Floucamafen (Saravanan and Kanakasabai, 2004 and Chanda Mallaiah, 2013). The determination of acute median lethal dose avoids the potential for ambiguity of making measurements in the extremes and reduces the amount of testing required.

CONCLUSIONS

The low LD₅₀ of Difethialone indicates its high toxicity to Indian desert gerbils and provides a strong evidence of the effectiveness of Difethialone as a promising rodenticide in controlling rodent menace.

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